
Education for Sustainable Development through Undergraduate Students

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Abstract:

Education for sustainable development is a vision of education that seeks to balance human and economic well-being with cultural traditions and respect for the Earth's natural resources. It emphasizes aspects of learning that enhance the transition towards sustainability including future education; citizenship education; education for a culture of peace; gender equality and respect for human rights; health education; population education; education for protecting and managing natural resources; and education for sustainable consumption. Education for sustainable development has come to be seen as a process of learning how to make decisions that consider the long term future of the economy, ecology and social well-being of all communities. Building the capacity for such futures-oriented thinking is a key task of education. This paper deals with education for sustainable development must explore the economic, political and social implications of sustainability by encouraging under graduate learners to reflect critically on their own areas of the world, to identify non-viable elements in their own lives and to explore the tensions among conflicting aims.

Keyword: Environment, Sustainable Development, Ecology, Social Wellbeing.

Introduction:

Education plays a crucial role for achieving sustainability around the world. It is the only medium that enables people to understand work for and benefit from sustainable development. Sustainable development is a development that addresses the needs of the present without compromising the abilities of forthcoming generations to meet their specific needs. The basic principle behind sustainable development is a combination of economic, social and environmental conditions that are shared by all of us. Education for sustainability utilizes the entire education system to provide students with what they

need to do to transform our societies to achieve a sustainable future.

Objective:

To explore the role of education in sustainable development.

Methodology:

One of the major crises in this century is the environmental crisis. Humans as one of the creatures that inhabit the earth need to begin to realize the environmental issues around them. The readers as the next generation must be educated well in order to raise their awareness about the present state of the environment. This study aims to emphasize how green literature could help to

encourage the readers to get closer to their environment. The qualitative research methodology is employed in this study based on the interpretative philosophy.

Literature Review:

When we go through the research already done in this area it shows sustainable development should include an acknowledgment and respect for the positive heritage and legacy of past generations. *Education for Sustainable Development* is a dynamic concept that includes a new vision of education that seeks to balance human and economic well-being with cultural traditions and respect for the earth's natural resources. It emphasizes the importance of learning in the build-up to the transition towards sustainability with additional education in citizenship education, education for a culture of peace, gender-equal opportunity, respect for human rights, health education, population education, education for protecting and managing natural resources and education for sustainable utilization.

Education for Sustainable Development:

It is the need of the hour that education needs to be transformed into a constructive tool for creating awareness among students and citizens of the world. Education for sustainable development uses multidisciplinary educational systems to develop ideas for permanent learning, nurtures respect for human needs that are compatible with sustainable utilization of natural resources and encourages an awareness of global harmony. Education for sustainable development has come to be seen as a practice of learning how to make

decisions that determine the long-term future of the economy, ecology and social welfare of all communities. Thus education for sustainable development provides a way to maintain equilibrium between humans and nature. The protruding Maharashtra has been lavishly granted with four seasons round the year. The nature has given the region lush greenery, beautiful dessert, Mountain ranges with its arms stretched; coastal area with bays and delta region; and innumerable water bodies. A region with rich resources of flora and fauna still striving with the quest: do people know about their environment? How should people behave responsibly towards the environment? The fear is alarming as the modernization which the human beings are enjoying, at the cost of environmental degradation, has resulted in various environmental problems not only for the creatures on the earth but also for the humans themselves. Human impact is the main source of environmental problems, while humans are also the answer to solving these problems.

Needless to mention, environmental issues are best handled with the participation of all concerned citizens, at every strata of the society and education. At national level, each individual shall have appropriate access to information concerning the environment that is held by public authorities, including information on hazardous materials and activities in their communities, and the opportunity to participate in decision-making processes (United Nations Environment Programme, 1993).

Thus, the research on environmental education finds it suitable through under graduate students who are pursuing their degree and very soon they will become the

responsible citizens of their cultured society. The reasons may be many, but most importantly, teacher not only teach students, but also shape their knowledge, attitude and behaviour by exerting a great influence through his/her own personality. They also write textbooks, help in curriculum development, and also guide locally in various issues. Thus, if they have the knowledge of environmental education, teachers may help their students to acquire environmental literacy as well as be environmental responsible citizens through inculcating attitude, interests, feelings, motivations, responsibilities and concern for the environment.

Generally, within the curriculum of Bachelor's degree, the Eco-feminism has found its place in the course Environmental & Population Education. The term Ecofeminism may be coined by the French writer, Françoise d'Eaubonne, in 1974, but it has special relevance in Indian diaspora. The environmental protection for sustainable development has found that women in India have a momentous role in running legendary movements at society and environmental-friendly practices at household. The role of women was very important in the success of movements such as *Chipko Andolan*, *Save the Bhagirathi*, *Save the Narmada Movement (Narmada Bachao Andolan)* etc.

Introducing environmental education studies in under graduate education curriculum is among one of those momentous initiatives. If a future well educated citizen is aware, he/she will be able to inculcate responsible behaviour among the others. As part of its efforts to create greater environmental awareness and inculcate responsible behaviour, India has

kept up with global trends ushering numerous policy reforms that call for environmental education and education for sustainable development have been framed to keep the environmental concepts and issues in the curriculum. As gender plays the social construct in Indian society, it is felt necessary to recognize the contributions of women folks in different movements to stop environmental degradation. Moreover, the daily chores, beliefs and practices in society should not be left isolated. The practicum and activity based curriculum designed for undergraduate student's education programmes help to identify and promote the pro-environmental behaviour. However, environmental education for sustainable development, designed for different levels of degree students, has long way to go.

Conclusion:

Our new education policy tries to inculcate valuable insights for sustainable development in education thought system. The curriculum emphasis on holistic well-being, environmental respect, and community values, offer a blueprint for integrating sustainability into education field. As the world strives to meet the expected outcome it will be helpful to incorporate the wisdom of good practices which can help foster a more sustainable, inclusive, and healthy society.

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